

Statistical Versus Conserved Quantity Information in Statistical Mechanics

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Statistical mechanics uses the notion of probabilities which we suggest means there is uncertainty in a scenario. In other words, some information, which we call statistical information, has been removed in order to simplify the problem. For example, a die has six sides and in a fully mechanical problem, one would have to analyze the forces etc on each side as the die is tossed. It is much simpler to replace the problem with one in which there is a probability which is the same for each side. In fact, we suggest that not only is information removed, but that one tries to remove as much statistical information as possible to obtain the simplest possible description. There may, however, be some constraints and so these restrict the extent to which one may remove information. Nevertheless, given a set of constraints which must be upheld, one may think of minimizing statistical information. We argue that this is the root of entropy maximization approaches in statistical mechanics.

In many problems there exists a conserved quantity, for example energy. This often appears in a constraint equation of the form: $E_{\text{total}} = \sum_i e_i p(e_i)$, where e_i are the single particle energies. Now, given that $p(e_i)$ is a probability depending on e_i , one might call $-e_i/T$ a second kind of information, namely conserved quantity information. One may write: $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ where F is the inverse function of $p(e_i)$.

It is possible to calculate an average of the conserved quantity information. In the Shannon case, it is: $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ and in the Tsallis case: $\sum_i p(e_i)^q \ln_q(p(e_i))$ where $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized. The point we wish to make in this note is that a priori the average conserved quantity information need not be the statistical information function which is to be extremized. In the Shannon and Tsallis cases it is, but not in the Kaniadakis case. In fact, even in the Shannon cases there are issues with an $\int F(p) dp$ differing from $\sum_i -p(e_i) F(p)$.

In (1), we see that in the Kaniadakis scenario, $\ln_k(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ where $\ln_k(p) = 1/(2k) \{ p^k - p^{-k} \}$, but the statistical information function is $-\ln_k(p)$ integrated over dp . Thus, taking d/dp undoes the integration and one may then take d/dp of the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ treating it as a Lagrange multiplier. Such an approach holds for any $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ provided one has the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$. (In the Tsallis case this does not hold.) This is associated with the statistical information, but is not necessarily the average of the conserved quantity information as in the Shannon and Tsallis cases.

We show explicitly that in the Shannon case, the recipe $-\int \ln(p) = -p \ln(p) - p + c_1$ which differs from $-p \ln(p)$, i.e. Shannon's entropy. Both work equally well in an extremization problem. We note that $\ln(p!) = p \ln(p) - p$. The Shannon approach is to use only $p \ln(p)$ whereas $p \ln(p) - p$ is more accurate. This could account for the difference in entropy expressions. The problem is that $\text{probability} = \text{product over } i p(e_i)^{N p(e_i)}$ for $N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ yields a Shannon's $p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ result without any use of Stirling's approximation. We also consider the Tsallis case.

The Notion of Maximization of an Entropy for a Statistical System

In this section, we ask: Why should the notion of an entropy function which may be maximized subject to constraints exist in statistical mechanics?

We first consider the notion of probabilities. We suggest that they imply uncertainty in a system, meaning that information, which we call statistical information, has been removed. In other words, given a die, one could analyze the action of forces on all six sides in a toss, or one may simplify by considering a constant probability of $\frac{1}{6}$ for each side. There is uncertainty due to the probability, but there is also minimal statistical information. In fact, we suggest that if one wishes to remove statistical information, one may as well remove as much as possible without violating physical constraints present. We suggest this is the idea behind the maximization of an entropy function subject to constraints. At this point, however, matters are abstract because no quantifiable formula has been given for entropy. It is simply an abstract function which must be maximized subject to constraints and is associated with what we call statistical information.

In many problems, one has what we call a conserved quantity information. In particular, if total energy is conserved then energy is conserved quantity. One may write probabilities in terms of e_i (single) particle energies, i.e. $p(e_i)$. Here we use an unnormalized probability. This immediately suggests:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((1))$$

F is the inverse function of $p(e_i)$ and so ((1)) is a somewhat trivial statement, given that both F and $p(e_i)$ are unknown. One could, however, measure $p(e_i)$ experimentally, as in an ideal gas, and hence find F . We argue that ((1)) demonstrates the structure of the conserved quantity information and cite three examples:

$$\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{Shannon-Maxwell-Boltzmann case} \quad ((2a))$$

$$\ln q(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{Tsallis case} \quad ((2b))$$

$$\ln k(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{Kaniadakis case} \quad ((2c))$$

We next point out that one may multiply both sides of ((1)) by $p(e_i)$. The inverse operation is division by $p(e_i)$. One might suggest that $d/dp(e_i) (-e_i p(e_i))$ is also an inverse operation, but it is not because $-e_i/T = F(p(e_i))$. Thus, one cannot simply multiply both sides of ((1)) by $p(e_i)$ and then take $d/dp(e_i)$.

One may, however, always do the following;

A. Explicitly take the integral $\int dp F(p)$ ((3))

Then, taking d/dp of this result guarantees that one obtain $F(p(e_i))$ which must equal $-e_i/T$. One may use $-1/T$ as a Lagrange multiplier and act with d/dp on $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$, assuming that this is a physical constraint. (It is not in the Tsallis case.). In such a case, $d/dp(e_i)$ may act on $p(e_i)$ alone because one is changing $p(e_i)$, but leaving e_i constant. This then is an extremization process and ((3)) is the statistical information function.

We have argued that such a function should always exist and ((3)) is a recipe for finding it. The problem is that one must know $F(p)$ a priori and this may be difficult.

Another issue is that ((3)) is associated with the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i)$ which may not be physical. For example, in the Tsallis case it is: $p(e_i)^q$ which is used. Thus, $\sum_i p(e_i)$ is purely mathematical in such a case and it is not clear if ((3)) has physical meaning in the Tsallis case. We consider this further in a later section.

We consider a specific example of ((3)), namely the Kaniadakis situation, for which we assume that one knows a priori:

$$F(p) = \ln k(p) = \frac{1}{2k} \{ p^k - p^{-k} \} \quad ((4))$$

((3)) leads to;

$$\frac{1}{2k} \{ \frac{1}{1+k} p^{1+k} - \frac{1}{1-k} p^{1-k} \} \quad ((5))$$

((5)), given in (1), yields $-p \ln(p)$, the Shannon result for $k=0$.

((3)) shows that one may begin with an equation associated with conserved quantity information and find the abstract informational information entropy function. An important point we wish to make, however, is that in general:

$$-\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = \text{-average conserved quantity information}$$

is not equal to the statistical informational entropy ((6))

((6)) applies to the Kaniadakis scenario.

$$p(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = \frac{1}{2k} [p^{1+k} - p^{1-k}] \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is not equal to ((5)).

Scenarios for which Minus Average Conserved Quantity Represents Entropy

In ((3)), we give a general recipe for entropy based on conserved quantity entropy. In the Shannon and Tsallis cases, however, one has the interesting situation that:

- $\sum p \ln(p) = \text{entropy} \quad ((8a))$ Shannon case
- $\sum p^q \ln(p) = \text{entropy} \quad ((8b))$ Tsallis case

$$\text{Here } \ln q(p) = \frac{1}{1-q} \{ p^{1-q} - 1 \} \quad ((9))$$

P in ((8)) and ((9)) is unnormalized. For the Shannon and Tsallis cases one has:

$P \ln(p)/dp = 1$ Shannon ((10a)) and $p^q d \ln(p)/dp = 1$ Tsallis

((8a)) and ((8b)) show that one does not have to perform the explicit integration of ((30)) and that average conserved quantity information (multiplied by -1) matches the statistical information entropy. These, however, are special cases we suggest.

What happens if one performs the explicit integration of ((3))?

In the Tsallis case: $S(e_i) = -\int dp p^q \ln(p) = -1/(1-q) \{ p^{2-q} / (2-q) - p \} + c_1$

$$= p^{1/(1-q)} \{ -1 + p^{(1-q)/(2-q)} \} + c_1 \quad ((10))$$

for $q \neq 1$ because $\int dp/p = \ln(p)$ in the $q=1$ case. Thus, one cannot consider the $q=1$ limit of ((10))

((10)) would have to be compared with a constraint $\sum_i p(e_i)$, but in the Tsallis case it is not $p(e_i)$, but $p(e_i)^q$ which applies for averages and so ((10)) does not make physical sense even though mathematically one may use ((10)) with a non-physical, purely mathematical $\sum_i p(e_i)$ constraint.

This differs from $S = - p^q 1/(1-q) \{ p^{(1-q)} - 1 \}$ ((11))

((11)) is the average conserved quantity information = $- p^q \ln(p)$.

We note that for $q=1$, it becomes $- p \ln(p)$ = Shannon's entropy.

If one takes d/dp of this quantity, then one obtains:

$$-q p^{(q-1)} \ln(p) - p^q d \ln(p) / dp \quad ((12a))$$

On the right hand side, one should take d/dp of $\sum_i p(e_i)^q (-e_i/T)$ and $d/dp \sum_i p(e_i)$. This latter constraint is linked with $\sum_i p(e_i) = \text{normalization constant for } p(e_i)$ unnormalized. Thus, ((11)) is consistent with an extremization process even though it differs from ((10)) which is custom made to satisfy an extremization process. At first it might seem that ((3)) does not make use of the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i)$, but when integrating one obtains an integration constant. If one sets this to 0 then there is no $\sum_i p(e_i)$ constraint, but if one does not then:

$$C_1 = c_2 \sum_i p(e_i) \quad ((13))$$

Thus, both entropies, which differ by more than simply a constant, are part of the same general extremization process. This begs the question; Which one should be used?

In the Tsallis case, the convention is to use: $\sum_i p(e_i)^q \ln_q(p)$ and not ((3)), because $p(e_i)^q$ is the averaging probability and not $p(e_i)$, while in the Kaniadakis case, one uses ((3)) because one cannot use an average of the conserved quantity.

Shannon Case

The Tsallis case is somewhat complicated because of the $p(e_i)^q$ averaging probability, but $p(e_i)$ is used in the Shannon case.

((3)) for the Shannon case yields: $-\int dp \ln(p) = -p \ln(p) + p + c_1$ ((14)) (see (2))

Formally, ((14)) is not the same as $-p \ln(p)$, but p is like part of a $\sum_i p(e_i)$ constraint and so one may actually have different entropies, i.e.

((14)) versus Shannon's $-p \ln(p)$.

One may note that $\sum_i p(e_i) = \text{constant}$, so this just shifts the entropy by a constant.

The convention is to use Shannon's entropy, although ((14)) may be used in an extremization problem.

Shannon's entropy, however, may be physically linked to the maximizing $\ln(N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!)$ using Stirling's approximation and also naturally appears in

$\prod_i p(e_i)^{N p(e_i)}$ for large $N = \prod_i \exp(N p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)))$ ((15))

One may note that in this case: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) - n$ ((16)) while one usually uses $n \ln(n)$. In this scenario, one sees that $p \ln(p)$ is an approximation of $p \ln(p) - p$ and that the latter is perhaps the more correct result.

The problem is that in the maximum probability of N trials for $N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$, one has:

Probability = $\prod_i p(e_i)^{N p(e_i)} = \prod_i \exp(p(e_i) N \ln(p(e_i)))$ ((16))

In such a case, no Stirling's approximation is needed and $p \ln(p)$ is linked with entropy. Using ((16)), one would not consider $p \ln(p) - p$ as entropy. Thus, there seems to be a dilemma, even though the two functions work equally well in an extremization approach.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we first argue that using probabilities means there is some information which has been removed from a system. We call this statistical information and argue that one wishes to remove as much as possible within physical constraints present in the system. This leads to the abstract idea of minimizing a statistical information function which we call entropy.

We suggest that in many physical problems there exists a conserved quantity such as energy. One may then write generally: $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, where e_i is the single particle energy and F is the inverse function of p . This equation holds for the Shannon, Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases. If one simply integrates $F(p) dp$ and then takes the derivative d/dp , one obtains $F(p)$. This must equal $-e_i/T$. If one thinks in terms of an extremization problem, then one may think of $-1/T$ as being a Lagrange multiple, and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ as being a constraint. Given that integration yields an integration constant c_1 , this may be written as $c_2 \sum_i p(e_i)$ yielding a second constraint even if $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized. Thus, one may obtain mathematically the so-called statistical information entropy from a relationship $F(p) = -e_i/T$ of the conserved quantity information.

We note, however, that in the Shannon and Tsallis cases, one may use an entropy which is $-\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ for the Shannon case ($F = \ln$) and $-\sum_i p(e_i) p^q \ln_q(p)$ in the Tsallis. This so-called entropy does not equal $-\int dp F(p)$, yet both are part of the same extremization process. This leads to the result that for the Kaniadakis case (see (1)), one uses $\int dp F(p) = \int dp \ln_k(p)$ as entropy, while one does not use this for the Tsallis case, but rather uses: $p^q \ln_q(p)$, i.e. the average of the conserved quantity information. In the Tsallis case, however, the integral $\int dp \ln_q(p)$ is associated with an average of $e_i p(e_i)$, but physically $p(e_i) p^q e_i$ is used and so there is a physical issue.

In the Shannon case, $\int \ln(p) dp = p \ln(p) - p + c_1$ which differs from the Shannon $p \ln(p)$. If one uses $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) - n$ as Stirling's approximation, then $\int dp \ln(p)$ is more accurate, but one may also obtain Shannon's entropy from $\prod_i p(e_i) p^q$ for $N \rightarrow \infty$ which does not use Stirling's approximation and only yields $p \ln(p)$.

References

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